

A Novel Image and Audio-based Artificial Intelligence Service for Security Applications in Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract

Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) can potentially reduce the accident risk while a human is driving. They can also improve the public transportation by connecting city centers with main mass transit systems. Creating a system that can provide a sense of security to the passenger, when the driver is missing, remains a challenging task. In this work, an image and audio-based approach, supported by novel AI algorithms, is proposed as a service to increase the security and trust inside an autonomous shuttle. The two modalities, running in real-time, can detect petty crimes scenarios such as screaming, bag snatching, people fighting and vandalism and enable notifications to authorized personnel for proper actions.

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1. Introduction

A self-driving car, referred also as an autonomous vehicle (AV) is a vehicle that is capable of sensing its environment and moving safely with no human input. The choice of autonomous compared to automated was made since, in the current literature, most of the vehicle concepts have a person in the driver's seat, use a communication connection to the cloud or other vehicles, and do not independently select either destinations or routes for reaching them, thus being "automated". The automated vehicles are considered to provide assistance (at various levels) to the driver. Moreover, public transportation systems progressively adopt the concept of autonomous mobility as a service (MaaS). In this context, there will be no driver (hence, no assistance can be provided), while the route and destinations will be defined autonomously by the associated fleet management system. The ultimate target of MaaS is to reach a system comprising of vehicles and services that independently select and optimize their destination and routes, based on the passenger demands.

On the other hand, the transition to fully autonomous public vehicles is not seamless and several obstacles arise in a real-world scenario. Several concerns of the end users can be identified regarding the safety and robustness of the AVs that are directly linked to the final user acceptance of the new technology. The prospective passengers fear several possible instances that could arise in case there is no driver in the bus. Indicatively, no person will be in the

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bus to perform first aid if required, while there is a feeling of discomfort being all alone in the bus at night, especially in certain neighborhoods. In addition, there is no authority figure present to keep passengers calm (e.g., school kids), whereas incidents of vandalism, bag snatching, indoor fighting, unaccompanied luggage may occur.

It is obvious that addressing the aforementioned concerns on social and personal safety and security into the vehicle, requires certain services to be implemented. For example, the detection of unaccompanied luggage and other personal belongings may raise a notification or an alert to the supervisor and/or the suitable authorities. This may be followed by appropriate notifications and/or instructions to the passengers. To the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of a complete system capable of efficiently tackling the aforementioned concerns, since current solutions are limited only to recording. This work aspires to introduce an artificial intelligence (AI) supported framework to significantly enhance safety and security levels in autonomous public transportation and increase passenger engagement. In addition, implementing such a solution will support safekeeping not only the users of the autonomous public infrastructure but also the vehicle itself. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data collection process and the proposed network architecture to employ the AI algorithms, Section 3 presents the preliminary results of this work. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. Implementation

The envisioned security service is designed to alleviate issues related to the absence of the bus driver and the increased threat from terrorism in European cities. Usually, incidents of abnormal passenger behavior and petty crimes are handled by trained drivers according to standard procedures adopted by the transport operator. In the autonomous shuttles, various sensors such as cameras and microphones along with smart algorithms maximize the feeling and the actual level of security.

2.1. Data collection and preprocessing

A plethora of petty crimes oriented datasets is required for the efficient development of the AI-based service. Thus, several data captures were organized to enable the required input. Initially, 13 different scenarios were simulated using two different camera perspectives for each one. During the second data capture, 29 video sequences were captured with 46,127 frames, demonstrating real conditions in an autonomous vehicle. Samples from the NTU-RGB [Shahroudy et al. \(2016\)](#) and the P-REACT [Dimitriou et al. \(2017\)](#) dataset were used to evaluate the generalization capability of the model. In the first stage of the visual analysis approach, the pose of each person in the frame is extracted (15 keypoints). In the second stage, a skeleton tracking algorithm is performed, associating persons across multiple frames. Regarding the third stage, the detected and tracked human body keypoints are represented as trajectories and during the fourth stage they are “fed” into a binary classifier, which classifies each action into normal or abnormal.

For the audio analysis, the MIVIA audio events dataset [Foggia et al. \(2015\)](#) is used. The MIVIA audio events dataset is composed of 6,000 events for surveillance applications, namely background noise, usually composed of several types of different sounds depending on the specific environments both indoor and outdoor (e.g., traffic jam, glass breaking, gun shots and screams). The dataset is analyzed in both time and frequency domains, to extract the spectrogram representations.

2.2. Network architecture

The visual analysis network consists of two bidirectional long-short term memory layers stacked together. The model is capable of binary or multi-class softmax classification. It contains three hidden layers of size (32×64) with the rectified linear unit (ReLU) [Nair and Hinton \(2010\)](#) activation function. For the audio analysis, two-dimensional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), that have shown great performance in recognition accuracy [Zhao et al. \(2019\)](#), are used. The focus of the work was to study the ability of 2D CNNs to generalize in different signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) conditions. For this work, the Adam [Kingma and Ba \(2015\)](#) optimizer was used and the ReLU activation function between the convolutional layers.

3. Preliminary results

After 50 epochs, the proposed model achieved a 96.22% accuracy. The time cost for feature extraction and classification is less than 0.05 s per frame for the classifier, since the model is relative shallow. Regarding the audio experiments, a batch size of 16 images was used and set the initial epochs to 200. The DenseNet-121 achieved a training F1-Score of 95.92% and a validation F1-Score of 88.74% for the case of 0 dB SNR. Regarding the case of

30 dB, the DenseNet-121 achieved a training F1-Score of 96.84% and a validation F1-Score of 91.82%. As expected, the network is able to classify the target classes with higher accuracy in the case of 30 dB SNR and it is observed that the training loss starts at smaller values, compared to the case of 0 dB SNR.

An experimental inspection dashboard for enhancing in-vehicle security is depicted in Figure 1. The services, running in real-time, employ an abstract common architecture for API calls that can be accessed either locally or exposed remotely via the network. Additional sensors, inside the AV, monitor environmental conditions (e.g., temperature and humidity), allowing the deployment of additional services that can improve the experience of the passenger.

Fig. 1. Experimental inspection dashboard for leveraging in-vehicle security

4. Conclusions

The automated in-vehicle services aim to replace the role of the safety driver and the essential functions he currently provides inside the shuttle. In this paper, state-of-the-art AI algorithms for video and audio analysis were adequately employed as the core of the envisioned security system. Novel prototypes featuring those algorithms along with camera and sensor systems inside the shuttle aim to revolutionize safety technologies and increase user acceptance, especially when AVs represent a large part of the transport means in public, as well as private transport systems.

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